

CAPACITY MANAGEMENT AND QUALITY SERVICE DELIVERY AMONG EMPLOYEES OF SELECTED SMES IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: *This study determined the relationship between capacity management and quality service delivery among employees of selected small and medium enterprises in Anambra State. Survey research design was adopted. The data generated from the questionnaires distributed to the respondents and were analyzed with descriptive Statistics and hypotheses were tested Pearson Product Moment Correlation co-efficient at 5% level of significance. The study revealed that there is no significant relationship between leadership capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. Furthermore, the study found that there is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. Conclusively, there is relationship between capacity management and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. Based on the outcome from the analysis, this study recommended among others, that SMEs management and policy makers should create clear and realistic job and organizational previews to enhance innovative capacity building which will result to quality organizational output.*

Keywords: *Capacity management, Adaptive capacity, Leadership capacity and Quality service delivery*

INTRODUCTION

The developments in industrialization globally have been at the forefront of nations to achieve sustainable development by providing cutting edge competitiveness hence providing employment, facilitating international trade, enabling efficient use of resources hence a major driver of poverty alleviation (Jackson, 2020). In the present dynamic and competitive business environment world, organizations are continuously investing in efficient and innovative tools and approaches aimed at giving them a competitive advantage (Ferreira & Coelho, A2020). Dekkers and Kanapathy (2020) noted that organizations that adopt adequate production capabilities while matching them with their organizational goals gain an advantage. This is the rationale for the focus on capacity management because since some of the staff are not competent to manage functions which they are hired for, the management of gap created by the system of recruitment in ministries is the management of the human capacity of the organization. Manu, Asiedu, Mahamadu, Olomolaiye, Booth and Agyekum,

(2021) defined capacity management as the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes in individuals and groups of people relevant in design, development, management and maintenance of institutional and operational infrastructures and processes that are locally meaningful. The continuous quest for quality product and service offerings prompted the business organization to adopt modern technology in their daily operation. Organizational products may differ from one firm to another; this may be due to the knowledge management in the organization.

Capacity management is the description of a special combination of professional knowledge, management skills, attitude and characteristics necessary to effectively carry out a task. The organization used as an effective tool to select, train and develop, evaluate staffs and develop human resource plans (Ubah & Ibrahim, 2021). Besides, managerial competence is a collection of all the competencies required of employees in an organization grouped into configurations appropriate to individual job or organizational role. Management skills groups are competencies that demonstrate the role of a manager. Managers cannot just stop at the stature of an expert but must have the ability to manage and lead others as well as lead the department to achieve the goals of the department and the organization. Managers are responsible for the performance of their subordinates and achieve their goals through influencing their subordinates and their partners. According to Omotayo, Anthonia, Hezekiah, Odunayo, Opeyemi and Odion, (2020) Management capacity includes knowledge of management, management skills and attitude of a manager to the job performing. Capacity management helps business sector to be effectively thereby developing their staffs through workshop, taking them on special training to enhance their technology skill, teaching their staffs departmental roles and how to attend to customer and how to make good use of time management. An organization that lacks efficient capacity management will have low productivity and will lack good communication skills in the organization.

The capacity management of an organization relates to whether it has the necessary skills, tools, and facilities to implement programs and manage operations (Ferlie d& Ongaro, 2022). It is against this back drop that this study examined capacity management and quality service delivery of employees in selected Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State.

Studies such as those by Kouzes and Posner (2021) and Amadi, Eze & Ogbodo, (2023) underscore the importance of effective leadership in managing capacity. Leaders who are unable to balance workload distribution, oversee resource allocation, and ensure employees are neither overburdened nor underutilized can jeopardize the company's service quality.

A major issue also lies in employee development and task accomplishment. As SMEs continues to diversify its portfolio, the misalignment between employee skills and assigned tasks becomes more apparent. Many employees may find themselves working on tasks that do not fully utilize their abilities or help them grow professionally, which stifles both personal and company-wide development. Research by Maslach, Leiter & Jackson, (2022) suggests that when employees feel their skills are not being developed or used effectively, job dissatisfaction increases, leading to higher

turnover rates. For SMEs, which is dependent on both skilled labor and high efficiency, this could slow the pace of task accomplishment and overall productivity. Lack of employee development also limits innovation, as employees who feel disengaged are less likely to contribute fresh ideas or suggest improvements to operational processes (O'Reilly & Tushman, 2020).

Moreover, adaptive capacity and staff innovation are vital to the long-term sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), operations. As the company scales up, it must be agile enough to respond to market changes and adopt new technologies or practices to stay competitive. However, adaptive capacity at SMEs may be hampered by inadequate workforce management, as poorly distributed workloads and lack of innovation-friendly environments reduce employees' ability to think creatively or solve problems effectively. Nguyen (2022) shows that when employees are overburdened or not encouraged to innovate, their capacity to adapt and introduce new solutions diminishes. This is particularly concerning for Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State, as industries such as oil and gas and real estate are constantly evolving, and the ability to innovate could define success or failure in these competitive markets. Inadequate focus on fostering adaptive capacity and innovation may leave small and medium scale enterprises, ill-prepared for future challenges, hindering both employee and organizational growth.

In summary, capacity management and quality service delivery issues at SMEs, are driven by gaps in leadership capacity, employee development, and adaptive capacity. Leadership that fails to balance workload effectively risks deteriorating service quality, which could lead to customer dissatisfaction and operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, underutilization of employee skills and lack of proper development programs impede task accomplishment and limit organizational innovation. Finally, poor management of adaptive capacity stifles staff innovation, making it difficult for SMEs, to stay ahead in fast-changing industries. To address these challenges, SMEs must implement more effective capacity management strategies, encourage leadership that fosters innovation, and invest in the development and engagement of its employees to unlock their full potential. Effective capacity management is essential not only for improving quality service delivery among employees of SMEs but also for securing SMEs position as a leader in its industries. The overall goal of this research is to see if there is a link between capacity management and quality service delivery among employees of selected small and medium enterprises in Anambra State.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between capacity management and quality service delivery among employees of selected small and medium enterprises in Anambra State. However, the specific objectives of the study include;

1. To ascertain the relationship that exists between leadership capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State.
2. To examine the relationship that exists between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State.

Conceptual Review

Capacity Management

Capacity management refers to the technique adopted by management towards ensuring that there is available skilled and talented staff in the organization with the right job behaviour (York, 2020). Capacity management comprises of the identification of gap in performance, organizing training and development programmes that will equip employees with needed skills to meet capacity demands of an organization. It is generally accepted that capacity management as a concept is closely related to education, training and human resource development (Williamson, 2022). Groot and Molen (2022) defined capacity management as the development of knowledge, skills and attitudes in individuals and groups of people relevant in design, development, management and maintenance of institutional and operational infrastructures and processes that are locally meaningful. This is a broader approach while still focusing mainly on education, training and human resource development. Therefore, based on this definition, capacity building for employees in a broad sense may refer to improvements in the ability of all employees to perform appropriate tasks within the broader set of performance standards of the organization. According to United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (2020), capacity building takes place at three levels, that is, at the individual level, an institutional level and the societal level. Capacity building on an individual level means the development of conditions that enable individuals to build and enhance existing knowledge and skills. Additionally, it requires the conditions that will allow individuals to engage in the process of learning and adapting to change (United Nations Committee of Experts on Public Administration (UNCEPA, 2021).

Institutional level capacity management should involve modernizing existing institutions and supporting them in forming sound policies, organizational structures, and effective methods of management and revenue control. The establishment of strong interactive public administration system that receives feedback from the population and makes public administrators more accountable and responsive is the goal of societal level capacity building (UNCEPA, 2021). Capacity building is perhaps one of the most fashionable, yet least understood term in the non-profit sector (Light & Hubbard, 2022). There is a lack of shared definition and understanding around its features and essential elements. Funders tend to talk about capacity building programs, while capacity builders might refer to capacity building engagements, yet organizations may refer to it as a set of activities or processes that accomplish a specific goal. There have been many different definitions applied to capacity building. Some authors have referred to it as a vague term that describes a wide range of activities, knowledge and resources that non-profits need to be effective, while others have focused on defining the process of capacity building (Connolly & Lukas, 2021). Throughout the literature there seems to be two definitions more commonly cited than others.

Connolly and Lukas (2021) define it as “a wide range of capabilities, knowledge and resources that nonprofits need in order to be effective”. In reviewing definitions, there are also those that encompass notions of capacity that extend beyond organizations. Capacity can also be built at the individual and community level, and therefore definitions need to include these concepts. The United Nations suggests that capacity building can be defined as the process by which individuals, groups, organizations, and communities increase their abilities to: (1) perform core functions, solve problems, define and achieve objectives; and (2) understand and deal with their development needs in a broad context and in a sustainable manner (Light & Hubbard, 2019).

Capacity management seeks to strengthen the ability of an organization or agency to achieve a desired outcome. Capacity building in this area can be defined as: “Supporting organizations to build and maintain the skills, infrastructure, and resources to achieve their mission”(Komimna, 2019). In order to effectively support organizations to achieve the above, understanding of the features and elements of organizational effectiveness is necessary. Too often, funders, capacity builders, and organizations are focused on the process of capacity building as opposed to the outcome of capacity building. Enhanced understanding of the components of organizational effectiveness can support capacity building efforts to be effective and targeted.

Leadership Capacity

Leadership capacity is the ability of all organizational leaders to create and sustain the vision, inspire, model, prioritize, make decisions, provide direction, and innovate, all in an effort to achieve the organizational mission (York, 202-). Not surprisingly, the classical principles of management focus on principles for enhancing productivity and increasing efficiency by designing a coherent organization structure (Mullins & Christy, 2021). Emphasis is placed on the division of work, and designation of responsibilities and duties for promoting the functional principle (Mullins & Christy, 2021). Personnel management is one of the significant principles incorporated in traditional organizations, whereby training and development programs, welfare programs, salary incentive programs, and upgraded working conditions are implemented (Analoui, 2023). The management process in modern organizations characterized by their open systems (Analoui, 2023), is considered a circular continuous cycle consisting of people working in groups aiming to reach specific objectives and focusing on human relations/ behaviours and social needs (Pindur, 2020). Employees perform better and are more satisfied when they are treated by senior managers as people, and when their innovative ideas are taken into account and encouraged by the senior managers (Kakabadse, 2017). The open system is more prevalent (Analoui, 2023) in modern organizations; it involves an informal structure where tasks are non-monotonous, knowledge exists at all levels of the organization, and interaction among employees is vertical and horizontal (Pindur, 2020). Communication can be both formal and informal; informal communication encourages different departments and hierarchy levels to interact more easily and share knowledge, and it is especially useful for team building (Analouei, 2023).

Organizations can be informal and flexible, thus characterized with more efficient communication and somewhat indeterminate relationships (Mullins & Christy, 2021).

Human capacity building is mainly enhanced by encouraging the participation of employee in decision making and by maintaining close relationships with the employees (Pindur, 2015). Senior managers in modern organizations advocate human capacity building through development of employees' professional skills and promotion of teamwork (Pindur, 2015). This is enhanced through the applied leadership style which is considered democratic; hence the power is more widespread (Mullins & Christy, 2021). The task culture is mostly incorporated in modern management organizations which sponsor change and adaptation; it is characterized by being a team culture where an employee can exercise more control over his/her work (Handy, 2022). Professionalism, respect and good relationships thrive in this type of culture (Handy, 2022). Effective communication and coaching from the senior managers to their subordinates can promote knowledge sharing, organizational learning, and effective leadership capacity building (Roddy, 2020). Continuous feedback and performance appraisal by senior managers are important for the employees' performance enhancement and motivation (Keegan & Den-Hartog, 2020). Higher work output and above average performance is measurable and awarded with higher wage rates as a motivation incentive, since it is assumed that the employee's only purpose is to increase his/her income (Kakabadse, 2017). Coordination between management and staff is considered crucial for improving productivity in terms of quality and quantity (Mullins & Christy, 2010).

Adaptive Capacity

Adaptive capacity refers to the ability of an organization to monitor, assess, respond to and create Internal and external changes (Okpanel, 2021). The concept of a "learning organization" is captured in this area of organizational capacity. It was stated that recognized leaders in the field generally focus on an organization's ability to "do things" to achieve, perform, or be effective in executing actions that support an organization's goals, mission, and sustainability. For instance, Dougherty (2023) define organizational capacity as the "the combined influence of an organization's abilities to govern and manage itself, to develop assets and resources, to forge the right community linkages, and to deliver valued services—all combining to meaningfully address its mission."

Adaptability could be defined as an effective change in response to an effective change in response to an altered situation (Kyap, 2021). Adaptability connotes the extent to which the enterprise is able to effectively analyze the unfolding trends, sense and undertake the necessary innovations and improvements of its products, service, business, structures, management style, business processes, models and strategies to adapt and excel in the midst of the emerging new changes (Banterhe, Carrares & Cavaliere, 2021). Business Adaptive Capacity lays the foundation for firms to improve their dynamic capabilities (Stefano, Peteraf & Verona, 2022). To edify business adaptability to emerging changes, firms must demonstrate prowess at four main capabilities, read, sense and act on signals, experiment, manage an enterprise's multi-complex structure and mobilize the relevant

resources (Reeves & Deomler, 2021). Ability of firms to read, sense and act on signal is enhanced by the use of a more advanced and structured information guttering by analysis system. In this process, the focus is often directed towards identifying the symptoms of the need for immediate and quick change (Reeves & Deimber, 2021). Strategic and operational intervention must not only be real time, but also aimed at bypassing usually stone rational decision making processes and hierarchies (Reeves & Deimber, 2021). As much as such a process can enable a business stay ahead of the identified changes, the success of the operational and strategic interventions to be undertaken often depends on resources availability and the executive willingness to provide appropriate conditions and environment for experimentation (Teece, 2019). An integrated Approach that permits experiment are not only latent in the development of a learning environment and trial and error without blame, but also significant use of technologies to integrate friendly online consumers in the testing and providing valuable feed backs that can subsequent be used in the modifications and the development of the new concepts (smith, 2019).

For Letts, Ryan, and Grossman (2022), organizational capacity is reflected in an organization's "ability to develop, sustain, and improve the delivery of a mission". Light (2024) describes capacity as "everything an organization uses to achieve its mission, from desks and chairs to programs and people". Conceptually, we think of organizational capacity as consisting of distinct domains that each represents an aspect of an organization such as governance, organizational culture, or technical abilities. While there is certainly overlap and interdependence among the various domains, segmenting organizational capacity can be helpful when assessing an organization's capacity and designing and implementing interventions to build capacity.

Quality Service Delivery

Quality service delivery can be defined in many ways e.g. the completion by an individual, company, or group of a task against known preset standards of quality cost effectiveness, and efficiency (Silzer & Church, 2020). In other words, quality service delivery is the total effectiveness of an employee or company against well-defined standards which include output, availability and reliability, response time, and cost efficiency (Williams, 2017). Many setups working under different conditions fail to clearly differentiate between the idea of performance versus potential (Wellins, Smith & Erker, 2019). Quality service delivery is more tangible, relatively easily identifiable, quantifiable, measureable, and comparatively short term. Potential on the other hand is latent, and presents the long term ability to consistently perform and improve. High performers may be good today, but may not necessarily be equipped to handle future changes (Françoys & Gagné, 2021). Because quality service is not mutually exclusive, it is all too common to confuse a high-performer for a high-potential person, and more often than not this proves costly.

Quality service delivery refers to the actual delivery of a service and products to the customer or clients (Lovelock & Wright, 2022). Relatively, service delivery can be described as a process, "the manner in which the outcome is transferred to the customer" (Mohr & Bitner,

2021). Shostack (2017) claimed that a service is a product that is a process, “a series of interactions between participants, processes, and physical elements”. Remarkably, service processes generally involve customer contact or /and customer participation (Shostack, 2017), which is often regarded as the most striking difference between manufacturing and service operations. Kellogg and Nie (2015) coined the all-encompassing term ‘customer influence’ to acknowledge the fact that in service the customer takes part in the process of production and delivery.

Empirical Review

Yamoah and Maiyo (2023) studied Capacity Building and Employee Performance in MTN Communication Ltd, Kaduna. The primary objective was to ascertain whether capacity building has a significant effect on employee performance, with specific reference to MTN communication limited, Kaduna. The study considered the aspect of capacity building that deals with the development of the individual or a group of people. With the aid of questionnaires, the researchers collected facts and analyzed them. The results of the study revealed that training when given properly has a significant effect on employee performance. However, the study also established that training does not always answer job performance problems. The study also concluded that reward systems such as: salaries, bonuses and allowances were the major ingredients which fuel performance of employees.

Douglas and Scotney (2023) carried a study on organizational capacity building in Reina Bird in Nairobi, Kenya. The study adopted descriptive statistics and questionnaire was used to collect data from 233 respondents. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data and Chi Square was used to test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between organizational and community capacity building in Reina Bird in Nairobi, Kenya. The study concluded that when there are adequate measures in place towards capacity building, employee show personal efficacy on the job. The study recommended that management should focus on innovative capacity building which will result to quality organizational output.

Mukwevho (2023) examined the capacity building as a means to enhance effective service delivery in the Public Service with much focus on Vhembe District Municipality. The scientific mixed mode research design for data collection was adopted in the study. Consequently, the tool for data collection in the form of the structured questionnaire and interviews was carefully designed and developed considering their reliability and validity as well as research ethical issues. Noteworthy, the stratified simple random sampling procedure was employed with the acceptable sample size of the respondents was selected. The data was processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The frequencies and cross-tabulations analyses were computed to determine percentage trend on responses of the respondents in each question. The chi-square analysis to determine the association at 95% confidence level ($P > 0, 05$) between position and HRD work conducted was computed. Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that the Vhembe District Municipality did not have a well-coordinated HRD system regarding policies and plans. It was therefore recommended that several policies be put in place to enhance the capacity of the employees within the municipality

for improved service delivery. In the contrary, the policy formulation process excluded the full participation of the auxiliary staff with the top and middle management fully participated in the process.

Denmark (2022) carried a study on understanding the concept of capacity building and the nature of land administration systems. The study was based on review of literatures relating to capacity building and land administration system. The study revealed that there are three levels of capacity building which are the broader system capacity building, organizational capacity building and group capacity building. The study concluded that capacity building is a main steam component that is addressed up front, not as an add-on. The study therefore, recommended that land administration system should be dealt with as capacity building projects in themselves for building the institutional capacity to meet the medium and long term needs.

Irefin and Mechanic (2022) examined the effect of employee capacity building on Organizational Performance with special interest in Coca Cola Nigeria Limited Maiduguri, Borno State. Both descriptive and explanatory research methodologies were adopted in this study. A five point numerically scaled Likert-Type questionnaire was constructed and administered among selected Staff of Coca Cola Nigeria Limited. The research hypotheses were tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The result showed that the level of employee competence of the Staff of Coca Cola Company Plc is very high. The study found that there is a fairly high relationship between employee competence and organizational performance; there is also a very high relationship between employee commitment and employee's turnover etc. The study recommended that management should hire employees who are likely to become linked to the organization; management should create clear and realistic job and organizational previews.

Karuri and Nahashon (2022) studied the effect of adaptive capacity on employee outcome at Central Bank of Kenya. The independent variable was talent attraction, talent retention, employee training and career management while the dependent variable was employee outcomes; i.e teamwork job satisfaction and employee engagement. The sample for this study was 130 staff drawn from the population of about 700 staff at CBK's head office. Confirmatory Factors Analysis (CFA) and stepwise Regression Analysis were used to analyze the data collected. The finding indicated that the impact of knowledge sharing on performances is not direct, it is mediated by talent management. The study also found that talent management positively affects organizational performance. The study therefore recommended the need for more extensive research on the innovation-performance relationship counting for the mediating role of organizational attributes and processes.

Tajuddin, Iberahim, and Ismail (2021) studied the relationship between capacity management and organizational performance in construction industry in Malaysia. The industry's innovation performance currently is reported to be amongst the lowest as compared to the others, which inspired this study to unveil the extent influence of innovation on performance. The instrument in measuring innovation and organizational performance specific to the construction industry were developed by

adapting measures introduced by several scholars in these fields. While innovation was represented by innovation design solution, innovation project practices and advanced technology utilization, organizational performance is represented by project and business performance. Contractors and consulting companies were the sampling frame of this study and the samples were selected based on a stratified sampling method to gauge representation of the different groups in the population. The results revealed that principally innovation is significantly positive in influencing organizational performance. The study concluded that the support of top management affects innovation (product innovation and process innovation). Furthermore, the results revealed that the synergy between organizational structure and information technology affects innovation (product innovation and process innovation).

Suhag, Solangi, Larik, Lakho and Tagar (2021) carried a study on the relationship knowledge retention with organization performance of the telecommunication sector. The independent variable is process innovation, talent retention and organizational innovation as an organizational culture as moderating variable. The research is survey research in which questionnaire is administered to 200 employees that are concerned with innovation in telecom industry present in Islamabad and Rawalpindi to ensure reasonable response. The data was analyzed through the SPSSv.20 software. Result showed that talent retention, process innovation and organizational innovation has a positive impact on organization performance.

Zafar (2020) studied the impact of employee capacity building on organizational development of telecommunication companies of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. The population of the research study was comprised of middle level managers of all telecommunication companies of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. Primary data was collected from 370 managers. Simple random sampling method was used for the selection of respondents. Questionnaire was administered to collect Primary data. Organizational development and employee capacity were building taken as dependent and independent variables respectively. Analysis of data was carried out by applying SPSS 20. Correlation and regression analysis tests were carried out to establish link between employee commitment and organizational development, and also to find out the predictor of organizational development. The study revealed a high degree of correlation between employee capacity building and its factors and organizational development. Regression analysis confirmed that employee capacity building is predictor of organizational development.

Hilmiana and Muizu (2020) conducted a study on the influence of personality on group capacity building and emotional intelligence of rural banks in west java, Indonesia, South East. The study adopted a cross sectional research design. The study used 233 respondents as research sample, taken by using proportional random sampling. The research analysis uses PLS-SEM analysis technique (Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modeling) in Smart PLS software. The results showed that personality significantly influences group capacity building. Personality is also a factor that can make a person's emotional intelligence high. The results also showed that group capacity is influenced by

employee willingness to learn on the job. The study concluded that employees who have a high level of emotional intelligence influences employee willingness to learn as well as employee relationship in the organization. The study also deduced that employees with a high level of emotional intelligence, viewed from personal competence and social competence, will be able to form a high engagement both to the work and organization or company. The study recommended that to build a high engagement, the company should be able to adopt effective group approach to learning.

Ahmed and Shaheen (2020) studied the impact of capacity building on organizational performance. Data was collected from the two major cities of Pakistan (Rawalpindi, Islamabad). Convenient sampling was used for data collection. Total 525 questionnaires were duly distributed and collected after completing from Lahore and Islamabad. Likert5 point scale has two extreme ends. Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient through Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected. The result of the study revealed a moderate level of interdependence between organizational performance and capacity building. The study concluded that capacity building has strong impact on organizational performance in an organization.

Stephen (2020) conducted a study on the influence of capacity building on employee engagement on the intent to leave of public school teachers in South Louisiana. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 244 useable responses to these instruments were completed by participating teachers. Findings revealed that the largest groups of teachers were of the Generation X age category. There were few significant relationships between the psychological variables and the demographic variables. Findings also indicated that the teacher's engagement were low due to the less attention for capacity building. The study deduced that capacity building is necessary for improved job engagement of teachers.

Obicci (2019) studied the determinants of employee capacity for organizational performance using the Ministry of Public Service in Uganda as a case. The study focused on types of employee training and development. Descriptive survey research design was adopted and Quantitative data was collected from 96 staff of the Ministry. Results showed that the staffs are not fully committed to the service of the Ministry of Public Service in Uganda due to poor skills and wrong training technique. The study concluded that capacity building components such as training, developmental programmes and technical skill techniques can improve the skill set of employees. The study recommended, the Ministry, among others should revisits its commitment strategy with a view to encompassing tenets of employee capacity building. Some important implications for future study are also derived from the study.

Khyzer, Ahmed, Shaf and Shaheen (2019) conducted a study on the impact of personal efficacy on organizational performance of three major cities of Pakistan (Lahore, Rawalpindi, Islamabad). On the bases of data which was collected from the three major cities of Pakistan (Lahore, Rawalpindi, Islamabad), it was acknowledged that organizational performance can be enhanced by involving

employees in decision making that will ultimately increase their commitment in the organization. Convenient sampling was used for data collection. Total 525 questionnaires were duly distributed and collected after completing from Lahore and Islamabad. Likert 5 points scale having two extreme ends. Pearson product moment correlation Co-efficient through Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected. The result of the study revealed a moderate level of interdependence between organizational performance and employee commitment. The study concluded that employee commitment has strong impact on organizational performance in an organization.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The reason for adopting descriptive survey research design is because the study intended to collect data directly from the respondents and descriptive survey research design is a research method that provides blueprint for the collation of data via primary source of data which is the use of structured questionnaire.

Population and Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The population of this study comprises of both managerial and non-managerial staff of selected seventeen (17) SMEs in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a purposive sampling method to select seven staff of each SMEs in Anambra State, given a total of one hundred and nineteen (119).

CarlCare Service Centre

Ekulo International Limited

A Challenge For Every Trader

Guinea Insurance Plc

MTN Office

Nexans Kabelmetal Nigeria Plc

Nigeria Shippers Council

Pokobros Industry

Sir Emeka Offor Foundation

Best Creative Easyway International Limited

Ceemetal Aluminium Industries Ltd

Chris Kingz Multi Gadgets

13DiceDin Ventures

International Textile Market Onitsha

Kris-willy Concept

Onitsha Chamber of Commerce & Industry

Ozen Garment Tailoring Company Nig.

Source of Data Collection

The study made use of primary source of data which is the use of structure questionnaire in the format of 5 points Likert Scale of strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Method of Data Collected

The relevant data were collected through the use of five point’s likert scale questionnaire which includes: Strongly Agreed (rated 5points), Agreed (rated 4points), Disagreed (rated 3 points), Strongly Disagreed (rated 2points) and Undecided (rated 1point).

Reliability of Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was obtained through a test-retest method. 20 copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents of Radopin Stores, Awka, Anambra State. The above organization is different from the organization of study. The questionnaire was redistributed to the same respondents upon testing the reliability a figure of 0.9 was obtained which shows that this instrument is very reliable.

Below is the table showing the figures and reliability figure.

Table 1 Reliability Test Table

OPTION	NO OF DISTRIBUTION	PRE-TEST	RETEST	DIFFERENCE	D ²
Strongly Agree	20	19	18	1	1
Agree	20	19	16	3	9
Undecided	20	12	11	1	1
Disagree	20	11	10	1	1
Strongly Disagree	20	12	13	-1	1
Total					13

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

d =deviation/differences

n =number of paired items

1 =unity

Substitute

d =deviation/differences

n =number of paired items

1 =unity

Substitute

Method of Data Analysis

Bio data collected were presented and quantified using simple mathematical tabular presentation based on frequency percentage. The data generated were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation co-efficient on Statistical packages for Social Science (version 23) at 5% level of significance was used to test the hypotheses.

Decision Rule:

Accept the Alternate hypothesis (H_a) if P-value is less than 0.05 ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$); otherwise accept the Null hypothesis (H_o).

Data Presentation

Out of one hundred and nineteen (119) copies of questionnaire administered, ninety three (93) were completed and returned, this represent 78%.

Table 1: Summary of the Questionnaires from the Respondents

Leadership Capacity	SA	A	U	D	SD
Management team of this ministry is competent in their functions.	30	41	0	22	0
All activities of this organization is flowing smoothly with the directives of management team.	29	40	1	23	0
Management has been able to look into the lapses of this ministry with necessary solutions.	27	40	0	24	2
Adaptive Capacity					
We easily apply new means and methods to make our services relevant	33	40	0	20	0
We have been able to upgrade some old tools to new one.	20	46	1	26	0
I can readily fill any role in this organization.	31	38	0	24	0
Quality Service Delivery					
I put more effort towards my task in this organization.	30	44	0	19	0
I am very active in sharing job ideas with other staff and colleagues in this organization.	21	46	0	25	1
I strive to complete my task within the expected timeframe.	27	45	1	20	0

Source: Filed survey, 2024

Data Analysis

The table below is the descriptive statistics that was computed to show the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum values, and Skewness-Kurtosis statistics, etc.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
LCP	5	1.00	121.00	55.8000	52.99717
ACP	5	.00	124.00	55.8000	54.23283
QSD	5	1.00	112.00	55.8000	50.69221
Valid N (listwise)	5				

Interpretation

The descriptive statistics for the independent variables, leadership capacity (LCP), and adaptive capacity (ACP) with the dependents variable; quality service delivery (QSD), were represented in table 2. The mean is used to establish a baseline. The maximum and minimum numbers, on the other hand, aid in the detection of data problems. The variation from the mean is represented by the standard deviation. It is a risk indicator; the greater the standard deviation, the greater the risk. The standard deviation is a metric that expresses how much each item in a dataset deviates from the mean. It is the

most reliable and extensively used metric. The standard deviations in the firms are 53.00, 54.23, and 50.69, for LCP, ACP, and QSD respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ha₁: There is a significant relationship between leadership capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State.

Table 3:: Correlations

		LCP	QSD
LCP	Pearson Correlation	1	.988**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	5	5
QSD	Pearson Correlation	.988**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Indeed, from the above figure, correlation coefficient of .988 shows a positive correlation between leadership capacity and quality service delivery. To have an idea of how much variance the two variables share, the coefficient of determination (R) is calculated. R is 0.988 x 0.988= 0.976. It implies that leadership capacity help to explain almost 98% of the variance in quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. From the above result, the study discovers that the confidence level between leadership capacity and quality service delivery is very high, and that correlation coefficient is not significant at 0.01 levels (.002>0.01). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is rejected whereas the null hypothesis is accepted which stated that there is no significant relationship between leadership capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

Ha₂: There is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State.

Table 4:” Correlations

		ACP	QSD
ACP	Pearson Correlation	1	.993**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	5	5
QSD	Pearson Correlation	.993**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the table above, correlation coefficient of .993 shows a positive correlation between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery. To have an idea of how much variance the two variables share,

the coefficient of determination (R) is calculated. R is $0.993 \times 0.993 = 0.986$. It implies that adaptive capacity help to explain almost 99% of the variance in quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. From the above result, the study discovers that the confidence level between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery is very high, and that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.01 levels ($.001, < 0.01$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate accepted which stated that there is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery in Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis, the study showed that there is no significant relationship between leadership capacity and quality service delivery Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. This result is contrary with the study of Douglas and Scotney (2023) which revealed that there is significant relationship between organizational and community capacity building in Reina Bird in Nairoobi, Kenya. Also, Denmark (2022) revealed that there are three levels of capacity building which are the broader system capacity building, organizational capacity building and group capacity building. Hilmiana and Muizu (2020) results showed that personality significantly influences group capacity building. The results also showed that group capacity is influenced by employee willingness to learn on the job.

Hypothesis two indicates the there is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. The result is in line with Karuri and Nahashon (2022) who studied the effect of adaptive capacity on employee outcome at Central Bank of Kenya, and found that talent management positively affects organizational performance. Likewise, Tajuddin, Ibrahimi, and Ismail (2021) results revealed that principally innovation is significantly positive in influencing organizational performance. The study concluded that the support of top management affect innovation (product innovation and process innovation).

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study determined the relationship between capacity management and employee performance Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. The data generated from the respondents were analyzed with descriptive Statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation co-efficient at 5% level of significance was used to test the hypotheses. The study revealed that there is no significant relationship between leadership capacity and quality service delivery Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. Furthermore, the study found that there is a significant relationship between adaptive capacity and quality service delivery Small and Medium Enterprises in Anambra State. Conclusively, there is relationship between capacity management and quality service delivery among employees of selected small and medium enterprises in Anambra State.

Based on the outcome from the analysis, this study recommended the followings;

➤ The study recommended that management should create clear and realistic job and organizational previews to enhance innovative capacity building which will result to quality organizational output.

➤ The management should lay the foundation for firms to improve their dynamic capabilities in terms of models and strategies to adapt and excel in the midst of the emerging new changes.

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